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Nutrition Knowledge Level of Teacher Candidates

Öğretmen Adaylarının Beslenme Bilgi Düzeyleri

ABSTRACT

This study, which investigates the nutrition knowledge levels of teacher candidates studying at Pamukkale University's Faculty of Education, was carried out by collecting data from 52 voluntary teacher candidates during the fall semester of the 2022-2023 academic year using an easily accessible sampling method. The research follows a survey model and is a quantitative study. Data collection was performed by using a scale form and the data collected were analyzed using the SPSS statistical program. Frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation test results were used in the analysis. Regarding the status of following written and visual media sources for nutrition information, most of the teacher candidates responded that they were not following the written media sources but were following the visual media sources. It was determined that teacher candidates were generally consuming fast food once a week. The majority of candidates described their dietary habits as "everything". Considering the factors influencing dietary choices, the most significant factor mentioned was "healthy and long life," followed by taste preference and practicality. Regarding the nutrition knowledge levels of teacher candidates, almost all of them accurately answered the question about the best way to lose weight, whereas most of them provided incorrect answers to questions about foods with the highest vitamin A content and foods with the highest iron content. It was found that the nutrition knowledge levels of male teacher candidates were lower when compared to female teacher candidates and that the overall nutrition knowledge levels of teacher candidates were at a moderate level.

Keywords: Nutrition, Teacher candidates, Healthy nutrition, Diet, Obesity.

ÖZET

Pamukkale Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesinde öğrenim gören öğretmen adaylarının beslenme bilgi düzeylerinin araştırıldığı bu çalışma 2022-2023 eğitim yılı güz döneminde kolay ulaşılabilir örneklem yöntemiyle gönüllü 52 öğretmen adayından veri toplanarak yapılmıştır. Araştırma tarama modelinde ve nicel bir çalışmadır. Veriler ölçek formu ile toplanmış ve SPSS istatistik programı ile analiz edilmiştir. Analizlerde frekans, %, ortalama ve standart sapma test sonuçları kullanılmıştır. Öğretmen adaylarının beslenme hakkında yazı ve bilgileri yazılı görsel medya araçlarından takip etme durumlarıyla ilgili olarak yazılı basında izleme konusunda hayır cevabı fazla iken görsel basında izlemede ise evet cevabı daha fazladır. Öğretmen adaylarının genel olarak fast-food beslenme alışkanlıklarının haftada 1 olduğu görülmüştür. Adayların beslenme tipi alışkanlıklarının en yüksek oran her şey olarak belirtilmiştir. Beslenme tarzı seçiminde en yüksek etken sağlıklı ve uzun yaşam olarak belirtilmiş ve bunu damak zevki ve pratiklik etkenleri izlemiştir. Öğretmen adaylarının beslenme bilgi düzeyleri ile ilgili olarak tamamına yakınının kilo vermenin en iyi yolu sorusuna doğru cevap verirken en çok A vitamini olan besin ile en çok demir barındıran besin sorularına ise tamamına yakınının yanlış cevap verdikleri görülmüştür. Erkek öğretmen adaylarının beslenme bilgi düzeylerinin ise kız öğretmen adaylarının göre daha düşük olduğu görülmüşken öğretmen adaylarının beslenme bilgi düzeylerinin orta düzeyde olduğu tespit edilmiştir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Beslenme, öğretmen adayı, sağlıklı beslenme, diyet, obezite.

1. INTRODUCTION

Nutrition is a vital subject for the sustenance and development of living beings. It is crucial for life and growth, starting from the mother's womb, for humans. It remains important during infancy, childhood, adolescence, youth, and the following developmental stages; nutrition is not only about satisfying hunger. A healthy, balanced, and mindful diet directly influences an individual's development and health. Therefore, having a high level of knowledge and awareness of nutrition is essential for an individual's own development and health. The increasing prevalence of obesity makes the level of nutrition knowledge a determining factor in preventing this issue among today's youth. This study aims to determine the nutrition knowledge levels of teacher candidates studying at Pamukkale University's Faculty of Education. This study is expected to provide data for acquiring insights about the nutrition knowledge levels of teacher candidates and to carry out studies in order to address any deficiencies in this regard.

1.1. Nutrition and Nutritional Knowledge

It should be emphasized that we live in an information society. Knowledge distinguishes individuals having knowledge from those, who do not. Nutrition knowledge includes the energy content of nutrients, carbohydrates, proteins, fats, vitamins, minerals, and phytochemical sources. There are still ongoing discussions regarding whether nutrition knowledge is explanatory and sufficient from the aspect of public health nutrition status (Korkmaz, 2010). The ambiguities, which individuals experience regarding nutrition knowledge, and the inconsistencies in their behaviors originate from uncertainties in this field. It is known that nutrition knowledge is necessary for any change to occur in consumers' food behaviors and attitudes, but nutrition knowledge alone is not a sufficient solution (Mazıcioglu & Öztürk, 2003; Worsley, 2002).

1.2. Nutrition and Its Importance During the Development Period

In the past, people were in search of food in order to survive and maintain their energy balance. However, today's individuals tend to consume delicious foods not just to satisfy their hunger but also for pleasure. This tendency leads to an increase in energy intake for pleasure rather than metabolic requirements, particularly during childhood and adolescence, contributing to the rise in the prevalence of obesity (Lowe & Butryn, 2007). Since healthy eating behaviors are acquired during adolescence, it is crucial to take measures to maintain body weight and prevent obesity during this period. It was reported that the problem of obesity, which has recently started to be seen particularly in childhood, is caused by an increase in dietary energy intake and a decrease in the level of energy consumption (Liberali, 2020; Sattar et al., 2019).

The consumption of high-saturated fats, added sugars, and processed foods has become widespread among children and adolescent individuals on a global basis (Bleich et al., 2018; Li et al., 2020). Moreover, the promotion and encouragement of unhealthy foods to adolescents on social media platforms and channels have become quite common (Potvin Kent et al., 2019). Understanding the processes that affect food choices during adolescence is very important in order to enable them to become physically and mentally healthier individuals in adulthood. The intensive consumption of unhealthy food items by adolescent individuals is associated with increased energy intake through the diet, an increase in body weight in adulthood, and a higher risk of chronic diseases (Poti et al., 2017).

The adolescence period is a very important time when individuals begin to make their own food choices driven by their desire for independence. During this period, the desire for independence influences food choices, and it often results in poor ones. In a study carried out on this subject, it was found that approximately 40% of the daily food intake of adolescents aged between 14 and 18 years consisted of low-nutrient, high-saturated fat, and high-sugar content foods (Krebs-Smith et al., 2010). Due to the lower level of instinctive control in adolescent individuals, along with mental development and changes, an increased likelihood of obesity has been identified during this period with an increase in body weight (Mason et al., 2021). The World Health Organization (WHO) has stated that over 340 million children and adolescents aged between 5 and 19 years worldwide are suffering from mild obesity or obesity (WHO, 2013). The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) countries has emphasized that the problem of childhood obesity has reached high levels, with adolescent obesity rates of 20.6% in the United States and 25% for children in Australia (Incleay et al., 2017). The Türkiye Childhood Obesity Study (COSI-TUR 2013) conducted among 7-8-year-old children showed an obesity rate of 8.3% and a rate of 14.2% for those with excess weight (TR Ministry of Health, 2015). As reported in the Türkiye Childhood Obesity Study carried out 3 years after this research (COSI-TUR II), the prevalence of obesity among children was found to be 9.9%, whereas the rate of overweight children was 14.6%. Mild obesity and obesity in childhood and adolescence remain a significant public health issue in Türkiye (TR Ministry of Health, 2015).

Regarding the rapid growth and development seen among individuals who are in adolescence period, it is considered highly important to meet the dietary energy and nutrient needs in order to achieve healthy nutrition. The goals of healthy nutrition during this period include ensuring optimal growth and development, enhancing learning and academic performance, enjoying meals, preventing nutrition-related acute health problems (such as obesity, malnutrition, iron deficiency, and dental caries), and protecting against nutrition-related chronic diseases (such as type 2 diabetes, hypertension, etc.) in later life (Garipağaoğlu, 2019; Yousefirad & Garipağaoğlu, 2019).

Skipping meals is one of the most common unhealthy eating habits observed during this period, and breakfast is the most frequently skipped meal among children, as indicated in nutrition habit assessments conducted in Türkiye and worldwide (Türkiye Nutrition Guide, 2015). Furthermore, adolescent individuals generally do not have a balanced diet; they tend to consume insufficient quantities of essential food groups, such as vegetables, fruits, and whole grains, while consuming processed foods excessively. Consequently, they have inadequate intake of folic acid, vitamins A, E, D, and B6, iron, calcium, zinc, magnesium, and fiber, and excessive intake of substances like fat, saturated fat, sodium, and cholesterol (Garipağaoğlu, 2019). Adequate and balanced nutrition necessitates the consumption of various food groups in every meal to increase nutrition diversity. In particular, it is recommended to daily consume dairy products, vegetables, and fruits, whereas foods with low nutritional value and high fat and sugar content should be limited. Among these foods, milk and dairy products constitute an important source of calcium and protein for growing children and adolescents. According to the 2015 Türkiye Nutrition Guide, the recommended portion sizes for adolescent food groups are as follows: milk and dairy products, 3 servings/day; meat and poultry, $\frac{3}{4}$ serving/day; eggs, $\frac{1}{2}$ serving/day; fish, 2 servings/week; legumes, 3 servings/week; nuts and seeds, $\frac{1}{2}$ serving/day; bread and grains, 4.5-5 servings/day for boys and 4-4.5 servings/day for girls; vegetables, 2.5-3 servings/day; and fruits, 2.5 servings/day (Türkiye Nutrition Guide, 2015).

1.3. Nutrition-Related Health Problems

Nutrition is one of the most important aspects of human life. Nowadays, it is evident that many individuals lose their lives at a young age or become unable to work due to excessive and improper nutrition, while another segment fights with difficulties caused by inadequate nutrition and hunger (Bilge, 2009; Sakar & Açıktur, 2019). Health problems would inevitably develop in case of not consuming enough of one or more of the essential food components necessary for nutrition or not consuming them at all (Çekal, 2008). It is stated that inadequate and unbalanced dietary habits lead to physical and psychological regression, behavioral problems, and mental challenges (Oktar & Şanlıer, 1999). It is well known that there are numerous chronic diseases originating from imbalanced diets. These diseases are generally listed as cardiovascular diseases, Type-2 diabetes, hypertension, osteoporosis, obesity, gastrointestinal issues, anemia, malnutrition, etc. (Besler et al., 2015). Being deprived of adequate and balanced nutrition is a direct cause of diseases such as beriberi, pellagra, scurvy, and anemia, and it also creates a conducive environment for the development of these diseases in some individuals. People, who lack adequate and balanced nutrition, suffer from experience immune system problems and become susceptible to illnesses, and the treatment of these diseases is often lengthy. Furthermore, when essential nutrients are not consumed at sufficient levels, the body cannot perform its functions fully, leading to the emergence of certain diseases (Bilge, 2009).

1.4. University Students' Nutrition

The late adolescent period, which covers the age range between 18 and 21 years, corresponds to the university student period. During this period, with the completion of cognitive development, there is also a development in the sense of ethics (Altay et al., 2018; Ermiş et al., 2015; Sakar & Açıktur, 2019). Nutrition has a significant importance in human life. Healthy nutrition can be achieved through the intake of the necessary nutrients in sufficient amounts and in a balanced manner for the human body (Altay et al., 2018). In this period, young individuals should have adequate and balanced nutrition to ensure proper growth and bone density development (Demir, 2008; Ermiş et al., 2015). The adolescence period is considered a special period, in which growth and development occur at the fastest rate, covering the transition from childhood to adulthood (Demirezen & Coşansu, 2005). Inadequate and imbalanced diet during adolescence not only affects academic success but can also lead to severe chronic diseases in adulthood, such as anemia, obesity, diabetes, and others (Akman et al., 2012; Ermiş et al., 2015).

It is emphasized that dietary habits that become a lifestyle are acquired by individuals during this period. It is important to note that during adolescence, there is a higher prevalence of problems such as insufficient and imbalanced dietary habits and dietary disorders (Baysal, 2012). If children in this period adopt adequate and balanced dietary habits, then they will benefit from advantages such as completing their growth and development on time and developing resistance to diseases. Children can mimic the eating habits of family members until the school age, and they can be influenced by the foods they prefer or do not prefer to eat. With the start of the school age, children who spend a significant part of their time at school partly take control under the supervision of their families and are influenced by their schools in terms of acquiring dietary habits. In this context, it would not be wrong to state that schools have important roles in enabling children to acquire proper dietary habits (Karakas & Törnük, 2016).

Nutritional needs that are specific to this period play an important role in achieving the desired level of growth and development. There is a significant increase in daily total calorie and nutrient requirements due to the acceleration of metabolism and an increase in socialization and activity levels during this period (Altay et al., 2018). The energy and nutrient components that should be obtained through the diet are as follows: Total fat should be more than 35% of the recommended total calorie intake and should not be less than 20%; saturated fatty acids should be less than 10% of total calories; polyunsaturated fatty acids should be up to 10% of total calories; monounsaturated fatty acids should make up the rest of the total fat calories. Carbohydrates should constitute 50-60% of total calories, protein should be 15-20% of total calorie intake (of high quality), cholesterol should be less than 300 mg/day, and in addition, fiber should be consumed at a rate of "Age +5" g/day (Aydenk Köseoğlu & Çelebi Tayfur, 2017).

Nutrients are categorized into four groups based on their nutritional components, taste, shape, and appearance (Baysal, 2012). **Meat Group:** This group includes foods such as beef, lamb, poultry and game animals, fish, legumes, and eggs. Foods in this group contain nutrients such as protein, iron, zinc, phosphorus, magnesium, and vitamins B6, B12, B1, and A, as well as fiber (in legumes). The food items in this group play a significant role in growth and development, tissue repair, vision functions, cell regeneration, and resistance to diseases. It is recommended that individuals in the adolescence period consume at least 3 servings from this food group daily (Köseoğlu & Tayfur, 2017; Karacaören, 2019).

Milk and Dairy Products Group: This group includes foods such as cow, goat, buffalo, and sheep milk, yogurt, and cheese. Dairy products like yogurt, cheese, buttermilk, kefir, and tzatziki are also part of this group. Foods in the dairy group are considered important sources of various micronutrients such as protein, calcium, phosphorus, magnesium, B2 vitamin (Riboflavin), B12 vitamin, and vitamin A. It is recommended that young individuals consume 3-4 servings of food items within the dairy and dairy products group daily (Köseoğlu & Tayfur, 2017; Karacaören, 2019).

Bread and Cereal Group: This group comprises wheat, rice, corn, oats, rye, and foods made from grains, such as flour, bread, cracked wheat, cereal, pasta, and bulgur. Grains are considered a fundamental food group for societies and are rich in carbohydrates. Wheat, rice, corn, rye, and oats, as well as products made from these grains, such as flour, bulgur, cracked wheat, and cereals, fall under this group. Cereals and cereal products are of great importance to health due to their content of vitamins, minerals, carbohydrates (starch, fiber), and other nutritional components (Köseoğlu & Tayfur, 2017; Karacaören, 2019).

Vegetables and Fruits Group: This group consists of all edible parts of plants. Vegetables and fruits are extremely rich in minerals and vitamins. They consist of 70-98% water. Therefore, they have very low-calorie levels. Variety in consumption is highly important within this group. Foods in this group are abundant sources of undigestible carbohydrates such as vitamins, minerals, and cellulose (Ermiş et al., 2015; Köseoğlu & Tayfur, 2017; Karacaören, 2019).

Fats and Sugars: Foods in this group are necessary for regulating body temperature and utilizing fat-soluble vitamins. They also play a crucial role in forming the building blocks of the brain and cell membranes, as well as protecting organs against external factors. Sugars are known as pure carbohydrates and are dense sources of energy. Excessive sugar consumption can lead to negative effects such as obesity and tooth decay (Köseoğlu & Tayfur, 2017; Karacaören, 2019).

1.5. Nutrition Problems of University Students

It can be seen that young individuals also have general issues besides their specific problems arising from being young. The most widely seen problems among them include nutrition, housing, education expenses, socioeconomic status, leisure time utilization, and health problems. Especially for students using dormitories to meet their housing needs, nutrition becomes a significant problem (Korkmaz, 2010). It was stated that young individuals in the age range of 18-24 years, which is also defined as the transition period from late adolescence to adulthood, have undergone significant changes in their eating habits and lifestyles in recent times (Ermiş et al., 2015; Garibağaoğlu et al., 2011). It is emphasized that young people in this stage generally do not heed the recommendations for healthy eating. They consume less fresh vegetables, fruits, and whole-grain foods, but on the other hand, they consume fast food, which is processed, fast, and ready-made, to a higher extent. Therefore, it is pointed out that they do not get an adequate amount of vitamins, minerals, and fiber when consuming excessive amounts of salt, sugar, and saturated fats (Baysal, 2012).

Nowadays, it is observed that young people are facing many health problems from both biological and psychosocial perspectives. Among all these health problems, diseases developing due to unhealthy and unbalanced eating habits are at the top of the list. Among the nutrition-related problems in young children and adolescents in Türkiye, there are issues such as underweight, obesity, and related problems, avitaminosis, anemia, common goiter, and tooth decay. In addition, it is stated that the problem of inadequate and unbalanced nutrition leads to a decrease in students' attention spans, a reduction in their perception levels, learning difficulties, behavior problems, absenteeism from school, and a decrease in academic success (Ayhan et al., 2012).

Although chronic diseases generally tend to develop during adulthood, the foundations of these diseases are laid during childhood and adolescence. Studies carried out on this subject indicated that young individuals between the ages of 18 and 24, also known as the transition to adulthood period, do not pay sufficient attention to healthy diet recommendations, do not eat properly, skip meals, and consequently, create a predisposition for chronic diseases. On the other hand, the age range of 18-24 years is seen as an opportunity stage for acquiring healthy eating habits and a healthy lifestyle. Therefore, university students within this age group have become the target population in numerous recent studies (Ermiş et al., 2015; Özyazıcıoğlu et al., 2009).

The beginning of university education is considered a significant period because of students' departure from the family environments they have been accustomed to until this period, becoming more open to external factors, and having the opportunity to make their own free choices (Yıldırım et al., 2011). The important characteristics of this period include economic challenges, the difficulties posed by the effort to adapt to newly established routines, interactions and learning processes with a diverse range of people of different genders and age groups, and increased susceptibility to external factors. During this period, young individuals may exhibit various health behaviors such as starting to smoke, engaging in sports, constantly dieting, and consuming alcoholic beverages. Naturally, this period marks the beginning of a new era in terms of nutrition, and the situations and events encountered during this period significantly influence eating habits. The number of daily meals consumed, skipped meals, reasons for skipping meal, and the type of food consumed between meals reflect individuals' eating habits (Onurlubaş et al., 2015). Determining the eating tendencies in students is very important to arrange eating habits in the adult period and preventing health problems that may arise due to inadequate and unbalanced nutrition. Previous studies carried out on the dietary habits of young people revealed significant issues related to nutrition during this period. Among these studies, students generally do not pay enough attention to meals, spend the day with only one meal, prefer foods like sandwiches and pastries more, economic problems lead to inadequate and unbalanced nutrition, and students residing in dormitories cannot eat properly due to the unfavorable conditions in the dormitories; they only manage to fill their stomachs (Korkmaz, 2010). Besides factors such as anxiety, low self-esteem, and changes in interpersonal relationships and interactions as a result of the search for acceptance in social media, women's desire and efforts to lose weight due to their esthetic concerns might also lead to eating disorders (Baysal, 2012). In terms of the prevalence of eating disorders, university students are considered a high-risk group. Adding the difficulties in adapting to new schools, environments, and dormitory conditions, combined with the lack of financial resources, to the mix, university students experience an increase in health problems related to nutrition due to unconscious eating and the consumption of fast-food type foods (Özyazıcıoğlu et al., 2009; Onurlubaş et al., 2015).

Obesity, which arises from increasing unhealthy eating habits of young individuals and decreasing activity levels due to the fast-paced lifestyle in recent period, is an increasing health problem in Türkiye and worldwide. In the TNSA survey conducted in 1998 on the prevalence of obesity in Türkiye, it was revealed that 33.4% of women were categorized as mildly overweight (BMI: 25-30 kg/m²) and 18.8% were classified as obese (BMI: 30 kg/m²). The 2008 survey, on the other hand, indicated that the percentage of mildly overweight women had risen to 34.4%, and the percentage of obese women had reached 22.7%. A review conducted by Pekcan (2011) emphasized that obesity related to poor dietary habits and nutrition-related chronic illnesses (such as cardiovascular diseases, cancer, diabetes, osteoporosis, etc.) have been on the rise in Türkiye. Although obesity has been perceived as a middle-age problem, the review indicated that it can manifest at any stage of life. Moreover, the same study reported that the prevalence of obesity (BMI \geq 30 kg/m²) among adults ranged between 18.6% and 30.4% in various studies conducted between 1990 and 2008 (Pekcan, 2011). The Türkiye Diabetes Epidemiology (TURDEP) study also highlighted a 44% increase in obesity over the past 13 years (Ayhan et al., 2012; Satman, 2011; Yıldırım et al., 2011).

Inadequate and unbalanced diet is considered a significant public health problem in Türkiye (Yıldırım et al., 2011). The desire of young individuals, particularly young girls, to have a shaped/grown body and an aesthetic appearance, coupled with the misconception that being thin equals to being beautiful, leads to unconscious dietary habits and the adoption of incorrect diets, thereby creating a foundation for eating disorders (Oluk et al., 2011). However, it is more related to what individuals consume during their meals rather than if they eat their meals. A study carried out by Yardımcı et al. (2012) addressed the preference of students for fast food-type foods. The research revealed that students primarily preferred chicken doner and hamburgers, followed by pizza, pita, kebabs, and lahmacun, respectively. Another study carried out by Güleç et al. (2008) found that students tended to consume chocolate, bakery products, biscuits, puddings, and ice cream for snacks. These foods, characterized by high levels of simple carbohydrates and energy values, are not recommended for a sufficient and balanced diet. As evident from the consumption of these foods in meals, students do not suffer from energy deficiency but rather have an imbalanced diet and generally prefer fast food (Onurlubaş et al., 2015).

Inadequate and unbalanced nutrition is reported to have negative effects related to physical development, including a decrease in body resistance, an increased likelihood of contracting diseases, prolonged treatment durations for acquired illnesses, and a significant decrease in the quality of life. Inadequate and unbalanced nutrition also has significant effects on social and cognitive development. Insufficiencies in these areas, which directly affect learning, can also negatively affect the use and development of learning skills (Oluk et al., 2011; Yıldırım et al., 2011). It was emphasized that individuals, who do not engage in sufficient physical activity, are exposed to a sedentary lifestyle, or have obesity problems, as well as those who do not maintain a balanced and healthy diet, are at a higher risk of developing various types of cancer. A diet rich in fat contributes to the development of serious diseases such as colon, uterine, prostate, and breast cancer. Stress, anxiety, discomfort, and feelings of insecurity and loneliness have been observed to psychologically influence individuals, leading some to overeat. Moreover, university students living away from their families tend to have significantly different lifestyles, and they are psychologically affected by this situation (Onurlubaş et al., 2015). It has been observed that university students without a family routine tend to skip meals and frequently consume food from faculty cafeterias and fast food outlets. As a result, these students may experience insufficient nutrition, leading to potential underweight issues or, in the case of excessive fast food consumption, obesity. In conclusion, university students represent a high-risk group in terms of both inadequate nutrition and obesity. Therefore, it can be said that close monitoring of young individuals in this age group is necessary in terms of energy intake, nutrient components, and disease risks.

The present study aims to determine the nutrition knowledge levels of teacher candidates studying at Pamukkale University's Faculty of Education and to ascertain whether this varies according to the personal characteristics of the teacher candidates. For this purpose, the answer to the question "What is the nutrition knowledge level of teacher candidates?" was sought.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. Research Model

The present study was carried out with a quantitative survey design. In this study, the nutritional knowledge levels of teacher candidates enrolled in Pamukkale University's Faculty of Education during the 2022-2023 Autumn semester were determined by using a scale. Survey models are studies aimed at revealing any existing event, phenomenon, or situation without any interference (Karasar, 2017).

2.2. Participants

Fifty-two 52 volunteer teacher candidates studying at Pamukkale University's Faculty of Education in the fall semester of the 2022-2023 academic year. Findings related to the sample of teacher candidates are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Distribution of Teacher Candidates' Personal Characteristics

Variable	Category	f	Percentage (%)
Gender	Female	42	80.8
	Male	10	19.2
Department	Science	11	21.2
	Preschool	8	15.4
	Social Sciences	3	5.8
	English	5	9.6
	Turkish	7	13.5
	Math	9	17.3
	PCG	8	15.4
	Music	1	1.9
Grade	1	2	3.8
	2	17	32.7
	3	29	55.8
	4	4	7.7

It can be seen in Table 1 that the majority of teacher candidates (80.8%) consisted of females. Of teacher candidates, 21.2% were in Science Education, 17.3% in Mathematics Education, and 15.4% each in Preschool Education and Psychological Counseling and Guidance departments. The distribution of teacher candidates across grade levels is as follows: 55.8% in the 3rd year, 32.7% in the 2nd year, 7.7% in the 4th year, and 3.8% in the 1st year.

2.3. Data Collection

The data collection tool consisted of two parts. There was a personal information form developed by the researcher in the first part, whereas there was a scale form developed in the study by Sakar and Akurt (2019) in the second part. The scale form contained 25 questions. Data collection was carried out by providing necessary explanations to volunteer teacher candidates at Pamukkale University's Faculty of Education, and they were asked to fill out the scales. The completed scales were examined, and those with missing information, personal details, or those where all items were filled out in the same manner were discarded and not included in the evaluation. This study was carried out with the approval decision taken at the 2023/11 meeting of Pamukkale University Social and Human Sciences Research and Publication Ethics Board dated 29.05.2023.

2.4. Data Analysis

The data analysis was performed using the SPSS statistical software. The responses of the teacher candidates to the questions were coded as follows: correct responses were coded as (1), and incorrect responses were coded as (0). A score of 1 point was given for each correctly answered question, with the highest possible score being 25 points. Accordingly, the scores between 13 and 25 points were evaluated as "good", those between 7 and 12 points as "satisfactory", and those equal to or lower than 6 points as "inadequate" in terms of nutrition knowledge level. The reliability of the data was tested using the Cronbach's Alpha test, and normality analysis was conducted by using kurtosis and skewness tests. The analysis results are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Kurtosis and Skewness Test Results

	Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient	Kurtosis Value	Skewness Value
Total	.827	-1.00	.09

As seen in Table 2, the reliability value of the data is 0.827, indicating a high level of reliability. The analysis of data distribution revealed kurtosis and skewness values of 0.09 and -1.00, respectively. Kalaycı (2016) suggested that data with values ranging from -1 to +1 should be considered to exhibit a normal distribution. Since the data have a high reliability level and normal distribution, parametric tests were employed.

3. FINDINGS

The analysis results regarding whether teacher candidates follow written and visual media tools for nutrition-related articles and information are provided in Table 3.

Table 3. Following Nutrition-Related Writings and Information on Written and Visual Media Tools

		Female		Male		Total	
		N	%	N	%	N	%
Following the written media	Yes	24	57.1	1	10.0	25	48.1
	No	18	42.9	9	90.0	27	51.9
Following the visual media	Yes	27	64.3	3	30.0	30	57.7
	No	15	35.7	7	40.0	22	42.3
Total		42	100.0	10	100.0	52	100.0

As seen in Table 3, regarding following the written and visual media sources for information and news regarding nutrition, more than half of the female teacher candidates (57.1%) stated that they follow such sources in print media, whereas this percentage was lower for males (10%). This finding indicates that, among teacher candidates, females are more likely to follow written media for nutrition-related information when compared to males. The percentage of those who answered “yes” to following written media was 48.1%, whereas the percentage of those who answered “no” was 51.9%. This suggests that less than half of the teacher candidates follow nutrition-related information in written media sources.

Regarding following the visual media sources, again, the percentage of female teacher candidates who follow these sources was 64.3%, while this percentage was 30% for males. The percentage of female teacher candidates following visual media sources is higher in comparison to males. In terms of following visual media, 57.7% answered “yes”, while 42.3% answered “no”. This finding indicates that more than half of the teacher candidates follow nutrition-related information in visual media sources. When comparing the teacher candidates’ practices of following nutrition-related information through written and visual media sources, it is evident that visual media sources are more prevalent.

The analysis results of teacher candidates’ fast food consumption habits are presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Fast Food Consumption Habits of Teacher Candidates

Fast Food Consumption Frequency	Female		Male		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Every day	2	4.8	-	-	2	3.8
3-5 times a week	6	14.3	4	40.0	10	19.2
Once a week	14	33.3	3	30.0	17	32.7
3-5 times a month	9	21.4	2	20.0	11	21.2
Once a month	8	19.0	1	10.0	9	17.3
3-5 times a year	2	4.8	-	-	2	3.8
Once a year	1	2.4	-	-	1	1.9
Total	42	100.0	10	100.0	52	100.0

Examining Table 4, it can be seen that the highest percentage of fast food consumption habits among teacher candidates is reported as 33.3% for female teacher candidates, stating that they consume it once a week., followed by 21.4% reporting 3-5 times a month, and 19.0% reporting once a month. In male teacher candidates, the highest percentage of fast food consumption is reported to be 40% for consuming it 3-5 times a week, followed by 30% consuming it once a week, and 20% consuming it 3-5 times a month. Overall, the highest percentage of fast food consumption habits is stated as 32.7% for consuming it once a week, followed by 21.2% for 3-5 times a month, and 19.2% for 3-5 times a week. Therefore, it can be said that the most common fast food consumption habit is once a week among teacher candidates.

The analysis results related to the nutrition type habits of teacher candidates are provided in Table 5.

Table 5. Dietary Habits of Teacher Candidates

Dietary Habits	Female		Male		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Vegetarian	6	14.3	-	-	6	11.5
Vegan	1	2.4	-	-	1	1.9
Paleo	5	11.9	-	-	5	9.6
Pescetarian	3	7.1	1	10.0	4	7.7
Ketogenic	2	4.8	1	10.0	3	5.8
Planetary	6	14.3	1	10.0	7	13.5
Diabetic	1	2.4	-	-	1	1.9
Gluten-free	1	2.4	2	20.0	3	5.8
I don't know	2	4.8	1	10.0	3	5.8
Everything	14	33.3	4	40.0	18	34.6
Pegan	1	2.4	-	-	1	1.9
Total	42	100.0	10	100.0	52	100.0

Examining Table 5, it can be seen that the highest percentage of dietary habits among teacher candidates was reported as “eating everything”, with 33.3% for female teacher candidates and 40.0% for males. This indicates that teacher candidates are not selective about their diet and claim they can eat anything.

The analysis results related to the factors influencing the dietary choices of teacher candidates are presented in Table 6.

Table 6. Dietary Habit Choice Factors of Teacher Candidates

Dietary Habit Choice Factors	Female		Male		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Practicality	5	11.9	-	-	5	9.6
Healthy and long life	20	47.6	3	30.0	23	44.2
Taste preference	16	38.1	6	60.0	22	42.3
Beliefs	-	-	1	10.0	1	1.9
Sustainability	1	2.4	-	-	1	1.9
Total	42	100.0	10	100.0	52	100.0

It can be seen in Table 6 that the most significant factor influencing the dietary choices of teacher candidates is “healthy and long life”, with a rate of 47.6% among female teacher candidates, whereas it is “taste preference” with a rate of 60% among male teacher candidates. In general, the most influential factors were indicated as “healthy and long life” with a rate of 44.2%, “taste preference” with a rate of 42.3%, and “practicality” with a rate of 9.6%. Accordingly, it can be said that teacher candidates prioritize their dietary choices in the following order, starting with the highest: “healthy and long life,” “taste preference,” and “practicality.”

The analysis results related to the knowledge levels of teacher candidates about the essential component of protein are provided in Table 7.

Table 7. Analysis Results on The Constituent of Protein

Constituent of Protein	Female		Male		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Incorrect	6	14.3	4	40.0	10	19.2
Correct	36	85.7	6	60.0	42	80.8
Total	42	100.0	10	100.0	52	100.0

It can be seen in Table 7 that the highest percentage of correct responses, at 80.8%, is related to the constituent of protein, which is the building block of nutrition knowledge for teacher candidates. It can be said that teacher candidates provided a very high rate of correct answers regarding the component of protein, which is the building block of nutrition.

The analysis results related to the item containing nitrogen that is essential for life, regarding the nutrition knowledge level of teacher candidates, are provided in Table 8.

Table 8. Analysis Results on The Item Containing Nitrogen Necessary for Life

Item Containing Nitrogen Necessary for Life	Female		Male		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Incorrect	21	50.0	6	60.0	27	51.9
Correct	21	50.0	4	40.0	25	48.1
Total	42	100.0	10	100.0	52	100.0

Examining Table 8, it can be seen that the incorrect responses (51.9%) constituted the highest percentage among the responses related to the element containing the nitrogen necessary for life given by teacher candidates. It can be said that teacher candidates answered the element containing the nitrogen that is necessary for life incorrectly in more than half of the cases. Therefore, it can be stated that teacher candidates largely do not know or have incorrect knowledge about the element containing the nitrogen that is necessary for life.

The analysis results related to the knowledge of pure carbohydrates by teacher candidates are presented in Table 9.

Table 9. Analysis Results on The Knowledge of Pure Carbohydrates

Knowledge of pure carbohydrate	Female		Male		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Incorrect	17	40.5	4	40.0	21	40.4
Correct	25	59.5	6	60.0	31	59.6
Total	42	100.0	10	100.0	52	100.0

Examining Table 9, it can be seen that most (59.6%) of the responses given for pure carbohydrates by teacher candidates were accurate. It can be said that the nutrition knowledge of teacher candidates regarding pure carbohydrates is largely accurate.

The analysis results related to the knowledge of water-soluble vitamins in terms of the nutrition knowledge levels of teacher candidates are provided in Table 10.

Table 10. Analysis Results on Knowledge of Water-Soluble Vitamin

Knowledge of water-soluble vitamin	Female		Male		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Incorrect	12	28.6	7	70.0	19	36.5
Correct	30	71.4	3	30.0	33	63.5
Total	42	100.0	10	100.0	52	100.0

Examining Table 10, it can be seen that most (63.5%) of the given by teacher candidates regarding the water-soluble vitamins were correct. It can be said that the information of teacher candidates about water-soluble vitamins is largely accurate.

The analysis results related to knowing the food with the most vitamin A in terms of the nutrition knowledge level of teacher candidates are provided in Table 11.

Table 11. Analysis Results on Knowledge of Food with The Highest Vitamin-A Content

Knowledge of food with the highest Vitamin-A content	Female		Male		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Incorrect	40	95.2	10	100.0	50	96.2
Correct	2	4.8	0	0	2	3.8
Total	42	100.0	10	100.0	52	100.0

Examining Table 11, it can be seen that most (96.2%) of the responses given by teacher candidates about the knowledge of foods rich in vitamin A were inaccurate. It can be said that teacher candidates' knowledge about foods rich in vitamin A is largely incorrect.

The analysis results regarding teacher candidates' knowledge of foods rich in calcium are presented in Table 12.

Table 12. Analysis Results on Knowledge of Food Rich in Calcium

Knowledge of food rich in calcium	Female		Male		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Incorrect	9	21.4	2	20.0	11	21.2
Correct	33	78.6	8	80.0	41	78.8
Total	42	100.0	10	100.0	52	100.0

When examining Table 12, it is observed that most (78.8%) of the responses given by teacher candidates for the foods rich in calcium were correct. It can be stated that the information of teacher candidates about foods rich in calcium is largely accurate.

The analysis results related to knowing the food that provides the most calories regarding teacher candidates' nutrition knowledge levels are presented in Table 13.

Table 13. Analysis Results on Knowledge of Food Providing the Most Calories

Knowledge of food providing the most calories	Female		Male		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Incorrect	16	38.1	7	70.0	23	44.2
Correct	26	61.9	3	30.0	29	55.8
Total	42	100.0	10	100.0	52	100.0

As can be seen in Table 13, most (55.8%) of the responses given by teacher candidates regarding the food providing the most calories were correct. The level of knowledge about the food item providing the most calories in female teacher candidates (61.9%) was higher when compared to males (30%).

The analysis results regarding knowing the food with the highest vitamin E content regarding teacher candidates' nutritional knowledge levels are presented in Table 14.

Table 14. Analysis Results on Knowledge of Food with The Highest Vitamin-E Content

Knowledge of food with the highest Vitamin-E content	Female		Male		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Incorrect	22	52.4	10	100.0	32	61.5
Correct	20	47.6	-	-	20	38.5
Total	42	100.0	10	100.0	52	100.0

As can be seen in Table 14, the highest percentage (61.5%) of responses given by teacher candidates regarding the knowledge of foods with the highest vitamin E content was that of incorrect responses. Teacher candidates seem to lack knowledge of and provide incorrect responses regarding foods with the highest

vitamin E content. It is also evident that all males and a significant portion of females are unable to identify the food with the highest vitamin E content.

Analysis results related to knowing foods with the highest iron content in relation to teacher candidates' nutrition knowledge levels are presented in Table 15.

Table 15. Analysis Results on Knowledge of Food with The Highest Iron Content

Knowledge of food with the highest iron content	Female		Male		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Incorrect	37	88.1	10	100.0	47	90.4
Correct	5	11.9	-	-	5	9.6
Total	42	100.0	10	100.0	52	100.0

Examining Table 15, it can be seen that the highest percentage (90.4%) of responses given by teacher candidates regarding the knowledge of the food that contains the most iron was that of incorrect responses. It is evident that teacher candidates do not know the food containing the most iron and they provide incorrect answers regarding their nutrition knowledge levels. It can be seen that all males and a significant portion of females are unable to identify the food containing the most iron.

The analysis results related to knowing the food containing the most Vitamin D in terms of teacher candidates' nutrition knowledge levels are presented in Table 16.

Table 16. Analysis Results on Knowledge of Food with The Highest Vitamin-D Content

Knowledge of food with the highest Vitamin-D content	Female		Male		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Incorrect	16	38.1	7	70.0	23	44.2
Correct	26	61.9	3	30.0	29	55.8
Total	42	100.0	10	100.0	52	100

As seen in Table 16, the highest percentage (55.8%) of responses given by teacher candidates regarding the food containing the highest Vitamin-D content were correct. Teacher candidates are seen to be aware of the food with the highest vitamin-D content and they have largely answered the question correctly. The majority of males answered this question incorrectly, while the majority of females answered it correctly.

The analysis results regarding knowing the food with the most fiber content regarding the teacher candidates' nutrition knowledge levels are provided in Table 17.

Table 17. Analysis Results on Knowledge of Food with The Highest Fiber Content

Knowledge of food with the highest fiber content	Female		Male		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Incorrect	33	78.6	7	70.0	40	76.9
Correct	9	21.4	3	30.0	12	23.1
Total	42	100.0	10	100.0	52	100.0

Examining Table 17, it can be seen that most (76.9%) of the responses related to knowing the food with the highest fiber content were incorrect. It indicates that teacher candidates were not able to identify the food with the highest fiber content and largely provide incorrect answers to the question related to this subject. Both males and females largely answered this question incorrectly.

The analysis results regarding knowing the food referred to as unsaturated fat among teacher candidates are provided in Table 18.

Table 18. Analysis Results on Knowledge of Food Referred to As Unsaturated Fat

Knowledge of food referred to as unsaturated fat	Female		Male		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Incorrect	27	64.3	8	80.0	35	67.3
Correct	15	35.7	2	20.0	17	32.7
Total	42	100.0	10	100.0	52	100.0

As seen in Table 18, most (67.3%) of the responses regarding the teacher candidates' knowledge of the food referred to as unsaturated fat were incorrect. It can be seen that teacher candidates were not familiar with the food referred to as unsaturated fat and they largely provided incorrect answers to the question. It was determined that both males and females answered this question incorrectly to a significant extent.

The analysis results related to knowing the food with the highest potassium content among teacher candidates are presented in Table 19.

Table 19. Analysis Results on Knowledge of Food with The Highest Potassium Content

Knowledge of food with the highest potassium content	Female		Male		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Incorrect	20	47.6	8	80.0	28	53.8
Correct	22	52.4	2	20.0	24	46.2
Total	42	100.0	10	100.0	52	100.0

It can be seen in Table 19 that most (53.8%) of the responses given by teacher candidates regarding the food with the highest potassium content were inaccurate. Considering their nutrition knowledge, teacher candidates couldn't identify the food item containing the most potassium and largely provided incorrect answers to the question. Although the majority of men answered this question incorrectly, more than half of the women answered it correctly.

The analysis results related to knowing the mineral group, which plays the most significant role in the formation of bones and teeth, among teacher candidates are provided in Table 20.

Table 20. Analysis Results on Knowledge of Mineral Group Playing The Most Significant Role in Formation of Bones and Teeth

Knowledge on the mineral group playing the most significant role in bone and tooth formation	Female		Male		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Incorrect	5	11.9	5	50.0	10	19.2
Correct	37	88.1	5	50.0	42	80.8
Total	42	100.0	10	100.0	52	100.0

As can be seen in Table 20, most (80.8%) of the responses given by teacher candidates to the mineral group playing the most significant role in the formation of bones and teeth were correct. Teacher candidates demonstrated a substantial level of accuracy in identifying the mineral group that primarily contributes to the formation of bones and teeth. While half of the male candidates answered this question correctly, a majority of the female candidates provided the correct answer.

The analysis results regarding teacher candidates' knowledge of the element responsible for carrying oxygen in human blood are presented in Table 21.

Table 21. Analysis Results on Knowledge of The Element Carrying the Oxygen in Human Blood

Knowledge of the element carrying the oxygen in human blood	Female		Male		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Incorrect	11	26.2	3	30.0	14	26.9
Correct	31	73.8	7	70.0	38	73.1
Total	42	100.0	10	100.0	52	100.0

It can be seen in Table 21 that most (73.1%) of the responses given by teacher candidates to the question addressing their knowledge of the element carrying the oxygen in human blood were correct. It is evident that teacher candidates have a relatively high level of accurate knowledge regarding the element that is responsible for carrying oxygen in human blood. Most male and female participants answered this question correctly.

The analysis results related to knowledge about diseases caused by iodine deficiency in the body, in connection with the nutrition knowledge levels of teacher candidates, "are presented in Table 22.

Table 22. Analysis Results on Disorders Resulting from Iodine Deficiency in Body

Knowledge of disorders resulting from iodine deficiency	Female		Male		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Incorrect	13	31.0	6	60.0	19	36.5
Correct	29	69.0	4	40.0	33	63.5
Total	42	100.0	10	100.0	52	100.0

As can be seen in Table 22, the correct response rate for teacher candidates regarding their knowledge of disorders caused by iodine deficiency in the body was 63.5%. Teacher candidates seem to have a relatively accurate understanding of diseases resulting from iodine deficiency. Most male teacher candidates answered this question incorrectly, but the majority of female candidates provided the correct answers. Male teacher candidates have a lower level of nutrition knowledge in this regard when compared to female students.

Analysis results related to the knowledge of deficiencies causing gum bleeding among teacher candidates are presented in Table 23.

Table 23. Analysis Results on Knowledge of Deficiency Causing Gum Bleeding

Knowledge of the deficiency causing gum deficiency	Female		Male		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Incorrect	32	76.2	8	80.0	40	76.9
Correct	10	23.8	2	20.0	12	23.1
Total	42	100.0	10	100.0	52	100.0

When examining Table 23, it can be seen that the responses regarding the teacher candidates' knowledge of the deficiency causing gum bleeding were generally incorrect (76.9%). Teacher candidates mostly provided incorrect answers regarding their knowledge of the deficiency causing gum bleeding. Most of both male and female students answered this question incorrectly. In this regard, the knowledge of male and female students is largely incorrect.

The analysis results related to the teacher candidates' knowledge of the foods prohibited in hypertension are presented in Table 24.

Table 24. Analysis Results on Knowledge of Foods Prohibited in Hypertension

Knowledge of foods prohibited in hypertension	Female		Male		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Incorrect	21	50.0	5	50.0	26	50.0
Correct	21	50.0	5	50.0	26	50.0
Total	42	100.0	10	100.0	52	100.0

Examining Table 24, it can be seen that the responses regarding knowledge of foods prohibited in hypertension are divided in half (50.0%). Half of the teacher candidates correctly answered the question about foods prohibited in hypertension, whereas the other half gave incorrect answers. In response to this question, half of the male and female participants answered correctly, while the other half answered incorrectly.

The analysis results regarding the knowledge of foods not recommended for individuals with high cholesterol among teacher candidates are provided in Table 25.

Table 25. Analysis Results on Knowledge of Foods Not Recommended for Individuals with High Cholesterol Levels

Knowledge of foods not recommended for individuals with high cholesterol levels	Female		Male		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Incorrect	23	54.8	7	70.0	30	57.7
Correct	19	45.2	3	30.0	22	42.3
Total	42	100.0	10	100.0	52	100.0

In Table 25, it can be seen that the responses regarding the knowledge of foods not recommended for individuals with high cholesterol levels were largely incorrect (57.7%). Teacher candidates largely provided incorrect answers regarding the foods not recommended for individuals with high cholesterol levels. It is also noted that more than half of both male and female candidates answered this question incorrectly.

The analysis results related to the knowledge of the vitamin causing blindness in case of a deficiency among the teacher candidates are presented in Table 26.

Table 26. Analysis Results on Knowledge of The Vitamin Causing Blindness in Case of a Deficiency

Knowledge of vitamin causing blindness in case of a deficiency	Female		Male		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Incorrect	13	31.0	5	50.0	18	34.6
Correct	29	69.0	5	50.0	34	65.4
Total	42	100.0	10	100.0	52	100.0

Examining Table 26, it can be seen that the responses regarding the knowledge of vitamins causing blindness in case of a deficiency were generally correct (65.4%). Teacher candidates seem to correctly identify the vitamin responsible for blindness when deficient. It is noted that more than half of both males and females answered this question correctly.

The analysis results related to the teacher candidates' knowledge of foods playing an effective role in tooth decay are presented in Table 27.

Table 27. Analysis Results on Knowledge of Foods Playing an Effective Role in Tooth Decay

Knowledge of foods playing an effective role in tooth decay	Female		Male		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Incorrect	8	19.0	4	40.0	12	23.1
Correct	34	81.0	6	60.0	40	76.9
Total	42	100.0	10	100.0	52	100.0

When Table 27 is examined, it can be observed that the responses given by teacher candidates regarding knowledge of the foods playing an effective role in tooth decay were largely correct (76.9%). Teacher candidates are seen to largely provide correct answers regarding the knowledge of foods that are effective in causing tooth decay. More than half of both males and females answered this question correctly.

The analysis results regarding teacher candidates' knowledge of the best way to lose weight are provided in Table 28.

Table 28. Analysis Results on Knowledge of The Best Way to Lose Weight

Knowledge of the best way to lose weight	Female		Male		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Incorrect	2	4.8	3	30.0	5	9.6
Correct	40	95.2	7	70.0	47	90.4
Total	42	100.0	10	100.0	52	100.0

It can be seen in Table 28 that teacher candidates' responses related to their knowledge of the best way to lose weight were largely correct (90.4%). Moreover, it was also determined that a significant portion of both male and female participants answered this question accurately.

The analysis results on teacher candidates' knowledge of the most nutritious food regarding their nutrition knowledge levels are presented in Table 29.

Table 29. Analysis Results on Knowledge of The Most Nutritious Foods

Knowledge of the most nutritious foods	Female		Male		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Incorrect	32	76.2	7	70.0	39	75.0
Correct	10	23.8	3	30.0	13	25.0
Total	42	100.0	10	100.0	52	100.0

Examining Table 29, it can be seen that the responses given by teacher candidates regarding the knowledge of the most nutritious food were largely incorrect (75.0%). Teacher candidates were found to have inaccurate knowledge of the most nutritious food. It is seen that the majority of both male and female candidates answered this question incorrectly.

The analysis results related to teacher candidates' knowledge of the amount of sugar that should be present in human blood are presented in Table 30.

Table 30. Analysis Results on Knowledge of The Necessary Amount of Sugar in Human Blood

Knowledge of the necessary level of sugar in human blood	Female		Male		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Incorrect	24	57.1	7	70.0	31	59.6
Correct	18	42.9	3	30.0	21	40.4
Total	42	100.0	10	100.0	52	100.0

It can be seen in Table 30 that the responses of teacher candidates regarding the knowledge of the amount of sugar that should be present in human blood were largely incorrect (59.6%). It can be said that teacher candidates mostly have inaccurate knowledge of the amount of sugar that should be present in human blood. It was also observed that a significant portion of both males and females answered this question incorrectly.

The analysis results related to teacher candidates' knowledge of the type of fat that the human body must necessarily consume are presented in Table 31.

Table 31. Analysis Results on Knowledge of The Type of Fat Human Body Must Consume

Knowledge of the type of fat that human body must consume	Female		Male		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Incorrect	30	71.4	7	70.0	37	71.2
Correct	12	28.6	3	30.0	15	28.8
Total	42	100.0	10	100.0	52	100.0

In Table 31, it can be seen that the responses given by teacher candidates regarding the knowledge of the type of fat that the human body must necessarily intake were largely incorrect (71.2%). It can be concluded that teacher candidates largely have inaccurate knowledge regarding the type of fat that the human body must necessarily intake. It was also noted that a significant majority of both males and females answered this question incorrectly.

4. DISCUSSION, CONCLUSION, AND SUGGESTIONS

Considering following nutrition-related writings and information on written and visual media, the percentage of teacher candidates who answered “yes” in the print media was lower than the percentage of those who answered “no”. It was determined that over half of the teacher candidates follow visual media for nutrition-related information. The findings reveal that students follow nutrition-related writings and information on visual media. Potvin Kent et al. (2019) reported in their study that unhealthy foods are widely promoted and encouraged to adolescents through social media platforms and various other channels. Previous studies suggested that these negative effects lead to malnutrition among children and adolescents (Bleich et al., 2018; Li et al., 2020).

As for the fast food consumption habits of teacher candidates, female teacher candidates reported the highest frequency as once a week, whereas male teacher candidates reported the highest frequency as 3-5 times a week. In general, the highest frequency of fast food consumption habits was determined to be that of “once a week”. Previous studies revealed that the intensive consumption of fast food leads to inadequate intake of vitamins, minerals, and fiber, with excessive consumption of salt, sugar, and saturated fats (Baysal, 2012; Özyazıcıoğlu et al., 2009; Onurlubaş et al., 2015). Such unhealthy and uninformed dietary habits, including consuming fast food, contribute to an increase in nutrition-related health problems (Onurlubaş et al., 2015).

Regarding the dietary type habits of teacher candidates, the highest percentage was reported to be that of “everything” by 33.3% of females and 40.0% of males. This suggests that teacher candidates do not have selective and specific dietary habits but are willing to eat anything. Numerous studies have pointed out that students' irregular, unhealthy, and careless dietary habits lead to nutritional problems (Onurlubaş et al., 2015; Korkmaz, 2010; Özyazıcıoğlu et al., 2009).

Regarding diet preference, the most significant factor was mentioned to be the healthy and long life for female teacher candidates and taste preference for males. Generally, the most significant factor was stated as healthy and long life, followed by taste preference and convenience factors. Previous studies frequently emphasized the importance of nutrition for a healthy lifestyle (Ayhan et al., 2012; Akça et al., 2013; Özdoğan et al., 2012). Studies indicated that delicious foods are more about pleasure and enjoyment rather than satisfying hunger (Liberali, 2020; Sattar et al., 2019). From this perspective, the priority of teacher candidates is considered positive.

Regarding the nutrition knowledge levels of teacher candidates, it was observed that over half of them answered correctly about the food that provides the most calories, the food with the highest content of vitamin D, and diseases caused by iodine deficiency. Likewise, they correctly answered questions about the constituent of protein, carbohydrates, water-soluble vitamins, foods rich in calcium, the mineral group that plays the most significant role in the formation of bones and teeth, the element carrying oxygen in human blood, the vitamin causing blindness in case of deficiency, and foods affecting tooth decay. Regarding the best way to lose weight, almost all teacher candidates provided correct answers. It can be concluded that teacher candidates have a high level of nutrition knowledge in these areas. Developing behaviors and attitudes related to the areas, where teacher candidates have sufficient nutrition knowledge, can be considered as a precursor to their healthy living. In this regard, Besler et al. (2015), Çekal (2008), and Özdoğan et al. (2012) suggest in their studies that maintaining conscious, sufficient, and balanced nutrition behaviors can prevent many chronic diseases.

Considering the nutrition knowledge levels of teacher candidates, it was observed that more than half of the participants provided incorrect answers regarding the element containing the nitrogen necessary for life, the food with the highest vitamin E content, the food with the highest potassium content, the foods prohibited for individuals with hypertension, food not recommended for individuals with high cholesterol, and the amount of sugar that should be present in human blood. However, it has been noticed that a significant portion of teacher candidates answered incorrectly about the food with the most vitamin A, the food with the highest iron content, the food with the most fiber, the food referred to as unsaturated fat, the deficiency that causes gum bleeding, the most nutritious food, and the type of fat that the human body must necessarily intake. It can be concluded that the nutrition knowledge levels of teacher candidates in these areas are low or very limited. Studies emphasize that students' nutrition knowledge levels are insufficient (Yıldırım et al., 2011; Özdoğan et al., 2012; De Vriendt et al., 2009).

As a recommendation, educational and instructional activities aiming to increase the nutrition knowledge levels of teacher candidates in the following areas can be organized: the element containing the necessary nitrogen for life, the food with the highest amount of vitamin E, the food with the highest potassium content, foods prohibited for individuals with hypertension, foods not recommended for individuals with high cholesterol, the amount of sugar that should be present in human blood, the food with the highest vitamin A content, the food with the highest iron content, the food with the highest fiber content, the food referred to as unsaturated fat, the deficiency that causes gum bleeding, the most nutritious food, and the type of fat that the human body must necessarily intake.

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